

Maximising the reuse of your data with good definitions

Following these simple principles, your definitions can make it easier to discover, understand, and reuse your data.

Remember, before authoring your own definitions, search for and reuse established ones if these are satisfactory. See "Further notes" below for suggestions on how to do this.

Suppose you want to state that a data set is about some "salt water". If you can't find a ready-made, well-defined term in an existing digital resource (such as in an on-line ontology: see **Further notes**), you can define it as follows:

1. **Be expressive.** The definition should be intentional, that is, describe the essential features and relationships of the item(s) of interest, and not just list examples. The definition should be broadly indicative, attempting to encompass the full scope of the concept, and not be overly "customized" to specific methodological realizations.
2. **Be brief.** Try to keep your definition limited to a paragraph or less. It should, however, expand significantly on the "label".
3. **Avoid circularity.** For example, defining "salt water" as "a volume of salt water" is not very useful. Never repeat the term in the definition. Instead, consider the next step.
4. **Identify (i) the broader category of things that your term belongs to, and (ii) what makes it different from other things in that category.** For example, "salt water" is a kind of water (broader category) wherein a portion of salt is dissolved (attribute that makes salt water different from other kinds of water). The general format is:

An **A** is a (kind of) **B** which **Cs**

Where A is the term you're interested in defining, B is the more general category, and C are the attributes, properties, parts or anything else that makes A different from other kinds of B. So we would have:

"salt water" (A)

is a kind of **water (B)**

which **has a portion of salt dissolved in it (C)**

5. **Don't assume shared understanding.** It's easy to forget that not everyone associates the same definition with a given term. This is especially true when working with specialists in a given discipline. In our example, if we were working with marine scientists, "salt" would be quite clearly associated with NaCl. However, "salt" can refer to many compounds, so we should probably say:

salt water (A)

is a kind of **water (B)**

which **has a portion of NaCl dissolved in it (C)**

6. **Avoid use of abbreviations, acronyms, and other "short cuts" in a definition.** It may feel strange at first, but this greatly helps reduce uncertainty. So:

salt water (A)

is a kind of **water (B)**

that **has a portion of sodium chloride dissolved in it ©**

7. **Reference, but don't feel restricted.** If there's an absolute authority on a definition (e.g. in a book or an article) and you're quoting them verbatim, then a "hard reference" makes sense. However, you may edit the definition to be more clear to non-experts and may generalise it based on your data. In the latter case, you should cite all the sources you consulted in formulating your definition and identify yourself or your team (e.g. via an ORCID ID) so your action can be noted.

Maximising the reuse of your data with good definitions

8. **Capture details outside the definition with “comments”**. Definitions shouldn't be too long. If you have more to say (for example, important exceptions, caveats, or things that you found ambiguous) add a comment to the term and possibly add links to further information.

Further notes

If a satisfactory definition exists, refer to it, rather than creating your own. In doing so, make sure you cite the DOI, GUID or (P)URL*, so the user can find it.

If a pre-existing definition is fine, but the term itself (i.e. the label) is not used in your field, request that a synonym or alternative label be added. For example, I have some data about a “chair” and I found this term and definition:

Label: “individual seating module”

definition: “A piece of furniture with a raised surface commonly used to seat a single person.”

Source: “<https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Chair>”

If the definition is on a digital resource, request the provider (ontology, wikipedia etc) that the term be updated to:

Label: “individual seating module”

Alternative Label: “chair”

definition: “A piece of furniture with a raised surface commonly used to seat a single person.”

Source: “<https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Chair>”

Finding and citing terms in ontologies

First, why might one need an ontology? <http://ontogenesis.knowledgeblog.org/1296>

To search for a term in an ontology a useful starting point is Ontobee:

<http://www.ontobee.org/>

Here you can either choose an ontology and search within it, or search for a term across all the partner ontologies. If you find a definition you like in an ontology or similar web resource you need to cite the (P)URL. It will appear like this (in this example where we wanted to find the definition of soil water content):

Class: concentration of liquid water in soil

Term IRI: http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/ENVO_09000026

Definition: The concentration of a liquid water when measured in soil.

Annotations

• **has_exact_synonym:**soil liquid water concentration; soil water content; soil moisture content

* Acronymns used

DOI (a Data Object Identifier): https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Digital_object_identifier

GUID is a 'Globally Unique Identifier' (or 'Universally Unique Identifier'). It is a 128-bit integer number used to identify resources. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Globally_unique_identifier

(P)URL (Persistent Uniform Resource Locator: <https://purl.org>)

To cite this guide

Specht A., Buttigieg P L., Garnier M., Schildhauer M. and Walls R. (2024) Maximising the reuse of your data with good definitions. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13579485>